

Renewable Energy and Energy Efficiency for Japanese RE100 Universities

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What opportunities do Japanese universities have to become energy efficient by changing to a sustainable building stock through renovation and rebuilding? How can Japanese universities cover the remaining energy consumption by means of a well calibrated spectrum of renewable energy, especially with solar heat, solar PV, geothermal energy and wood biomass energy?

Keywords: renewable energy, PV, solar heat, geothermal energy, biomass energy, energy efficiency, sustainable building

Energy Efficiency

Japanese universities have an enormous largely untapped potential to reduce their energy consumption by means of sustainable energy efficient renovation and new zero- or plus-energy buildings. For that purpose, it is essential that universities begin to look at whole life cost, energy and carbon analysis of buildings. Furthermore, universities can and should set their own sustainability goals for renovation and new building projects.

Universities are in a good position to become front runners in sustainable energy efficient architecture combining their own knowledge and research expertise with modern methods and standards developed all over the world. The currently dominating Japanese building industry trend is focus on active high technology, while in other parts of the world the focus is more on the passively energy efficient building envelop, combined with a few robust and cost efficient renewable energy systems.

Renewable Energy

Japan is in the enviable position of being competitively rich in renewable energy. Solar irradiation is comparable to southern Europe, making solar heat collection and solar PV arrays and rooftop more cost efficient than in Germany. Furthermore, Japan is among the world's three best countries regarding its national geothermal energy resources [4]. And in the long term universities can reduce their energy costs by investing in ground source heat pumps for heating in the winter and cooling in the summer. Moreover, Japan is covered by 70% with fast growing and mostly unharvested forests. Modern wood gas cogeneration offers a stable, affordable long term option flexibly convert wood chips into heat and electricity [1,3,5]. Solar heat, buffered by heat storage tanks is mildly weather dependent. Solar PV is weather dependent, but can be stabilized by the complimentary use of wood gas cogeneration.

Energy Ethics

What kind of energy supply will be adopted locally and nationwide, finally does not depend on the available technology and instruments of finance. Prior to these considerations are fundamental decisions on religious, human and environmental ethics. Universities have the capacity to critically think about these existential questions not from a narrow materialistic

natural science perspective, but can apply a holistic ethical perspective. Such a perspective may be instrumental in overcoming local development limits and inflexibility in adopting new innovative solutions [2].

Conclusion

In the interest of their own economic survival and in the interest of teaching students and society by way of good example on how to implement critical SDGs, universities in Japan may be well advised to adopt their own RE100 strategies, and become able to spin off well tested solutions to the benefit of wider society.

References

- [1] Eckhard Hitzer, *European Trends in Wood Biomass Energy Cogeneration*, Sophia Journal of European Studies, Vol. 10, pp. 191-205, 2018. Open Access: <http://digital-archives.sophia.ac.jp/repository/view/repository/20180412010>
- [2] Eckhard Hitzer, *Christ Centered Stewardship for the Environment*, 2016. Preprint: <http://vixra.org/abs/1710.0008>
- [3] Eckhard Hitzer, N. Miyazaki, M. Langager, T. Kibe, *Prospects of Modern Wood Gas Cogeneration Renewable Energy Supply in Japan – Case Study of ICU*, 2015. Preprint: <http://vixra.org/abs/1710.0009>
- [4] Eckhard Hitzer, *The true riches of Japan: High tech and natural energy can secure Japan's peace and prosperity, and give a new sustainable peace and prosperity dimension to its overseas development aid*, Peace Reports of the International Christian University Peace Research Institute, Vol. 10, No. 2, Oct. 2015, pp. 9-11. Preprint: <http://vixra.org/abs/1511.0301>
- [5] Eckhard Hitzer, Mark Langager, Nobuyuki Miyazaki, Takashi Kibe, *Report on the Activities for ICU Research Grant-In-Aid*, version of 28 Aug. 2015 (submitted to ICU Research Support Group).